

DISTANCE BETWEEN ACIDIC AND BASIC SIDE CHAINS IN HORN KERATIN

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(Received May 28, 1955)

From the models of α -keratin depicted by Astbury¹ it is found that three amino acid residues take up a distance of about 5.1 A. along the fibre axis. If the number of residues separating a basic and an acidic side chain can be found out, the distance between them can be easily calculated. For this purpose the equivalent weight of horn was first determined.

The amphoteric nature of horn keratin has already been discussed by the author.² It is, therefore, possible to find out the acid or base combining capacity of horn protein by means of titration. As base combining results were found to be more reliable than those with acid the base combining capacity of horn was determined. For this purpose, 2.5 g. of buffalo horn powder obtained in a manner described earlier³ was treated with 100 c.c. of NaOH solution (1.6 N/10) for absorption of the latter, after which it was filtered,

FIG. 1
Titration curve for horn.
(Temp. = 30°).

washed with distilled water and the filtrate made to 500 c.c. A blank titration curve was obtained by taking 100 c.c. of the original (1.6 N/10) NaOH solution diluted to 500 c.c. 25 c.c. of these stock solutions were taken for each titration with N/10 oxalic acid, the volume of acid added and the corresponding E.M.F.

were recorded; the whole experiment was carried out in the hydrogen electrode system. The blank curve as well as the titration curve are shown in Fig. 1.

It will be observed that some amount of alkali has been consumed by horn, and since isoelectric protein does not contain any bound ions, the amount of alkali consumed at this point must have reacted with the protein. For this reason, the amount of alkali really consumed by horn at p_H 4.0 (isoelectric point of horn determined previously by the author) may be taken as involved in chemical reaction with horn protein. From the graph it is found that 1.9 c.c. of $N/10$ $NaOH$ have combined with 25 c.c. horn solution. Therefore, 500 c.c. horn solution (2.5 g. horn) will combine with 38 c.c. of $N/10$ $NaOH$ (0.152 g.). In other words, 40 g. of $NaOH$ will combine with 657.8 g. of horn which is, therefore, the equivalent weight of horn. It is quite likely that some amount of alkali has been used in hydrolysing protein in which case the amount of alkali really in combination with protein is less, consequently the true equivalent weight would increase.

Since each acidic side chain reacts presumably with one molecule of $NaOH$, there must on the average be present in each 658 g. of horn one acidic side chain. Now the average weight of the amino-acid residues is about 120¹. This means that one acidic side chain occurs not more than once in about 6 residues (drawing in round figure and considering that the actual eq. wt. is a little higher). As there are roughly as many acidic side chains as basic, it may be concluded that the basic and acidic side chains are separated by about the length of 3 residues *i. e.* 5.1 Å

Thanks are due to Prof. J. K. Chowdhury for his keen interest in the work.

R E F E R E N C E S

1. Astbury, "Fundamentals of Fibre Structure", 1933, p. 177.
2. Bandyopadhyay, *this Journal*, 1948, 11, 148.